

VALUES EDUCATION IN A POSTMODERN CONTEXT. A QUALITATIVE PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

Values education is an indispensable formative core of any educational system, but in the context of postmodernity, this dimension has often been relativized, fragmented and subjected to radical cultural reinterpretations. The present study proposes a theoretical and critical analysis of how values education can be re-signified in a world characterized by epistemological pluralism, moral uncertainty and identity diversity.

The paper first explores the fundamental concepts of axiological education and postmodern education, followed by the integration of Lawrence Kohlberg's theory of psycho-moral development (1958, 1981) as a psychological foundation for understanding the process of internalizing values. At the center of the analysis

is the relationship between the values of democracy – respect for human rights, freedom of expression, solidarity and social justice – and the current challenges generated by the rise of nationalism and extremism in the global context.

The study supports the idea that values education should not be abandoned in the name of postmodern pluralism, but reconfigured in a reflective and dialogic framework. The training of teachers and young people must include moral, intercultural and democratic competences, and education itself must become a space for the critical construction of common values. From this perspective, values education in a postmodern context becomes not only a pedagogical issue, but one of democratic and moral survival of contemporary societies.

Keywords: Education through values, Postmodernism, Psycho-moral development, Democracy, Teacher training.

1. Introduction

In recent decades, debates about education have been strongly marked by the tension between postmodern pluralism and the need for axiological cohesion at the social level. On the one hand, the postmodern perspective denounces unifying metanarratives and privileges diversity, contextualism and the negotiation of meanings (Lyotard, 1979; Bauman, 1993; Giroux, 1997). On the other hand, democratic regimes depend on a minimum ethical consensus - respect for dignity, rights, law, dialogue and nonviolence - without which pluralism risks degenerating into fragmentation, polarization and normative cynicism. In educational terms, this tension translates into the central question of our study: how can education through values be re-signified in a postmodern context, so as to support democracy in the face of contemporary trends of nationalism and extremism?

Recent comparative data suggest that civic space and the quality of democracy have eroded globally, raising the stakes for values-based education.

The Freedom in the World 2024 report shows the 18th consecutive year of decline in global freedom, with deteriorations in political rights and civil liberties in 52 countries (Freedom House, 2024). The trend has continued in the following years, with the synthesis report confirming the persistence of democratic decline worldwide (Freedom House, 2025). These dynamics are accompanied by authoritarian populism and the normalization of exclusivist discourses, which amplifies the pressure on education to produce not only skills, but also civic character and moral criteria for living together in difference (Freedom House, 2024, 2025).

In this context, international educational policies have advanced in two complementary directions. The first direction is Education for Sustainable Development (ESD), anchored in the 2030 Agenda and SDG 4, where UNESCO proposes ESD for 2030 - A Roadmap as a systemic implementation architecture, explicitly emphasizing the role of values, attitudes and competences for transformation (UNESCO, 2020). The second direction is democratic and intercultural competence, formalized by the Council of Europe in the Reference Framework of Competences for Democratic Culture (RFCDC), which defines a coherent set of values, attitudes, knowledge/critical understanding and skills necessary to participate in a culture of democracy (Council of Europe, 2018). Together, the two frameworks provide a common language and curriculum design tools to link education through values to civic practices and sustainability.

In parallel, the OECD introduced the assessment of global competence in PISA in 2018, emphasizing students' ability to examine local/global issues, to interact openly and effectively interculturally, and to act for the common good and sustainable development (OECD, 2018a; 2018b). This shift shifts the focus from “what you know” to “what you can do with what you know” in diverse

societies, reinforcing the argument that values education must be practical, situational, and action-oriented.

However, the literature in the field also presents critical, opposing approaches, warning that ESD can become “feel-good education” if it reduces moral complexity to consensual slogans, avoiding confronting the real dilemmas of power, justice, and accountability (Jickling & Wals, 2008, 2012). In the same spirit, Sterling (2010) argues for transformative learning, capable of changing mental frames and supporting institutional transitions, not just adding “green” content to the curriculum. Thus, the issue is not the simple inclusion of values, but how they are lived, problematized and internalized in real, sometimes controversial contexts.

Against this background, from a psychological perspective, Lawrence Kohlberg's theory of psycho-moral development (1981, 1984) provides a solid basis for understanding how individuals move from normative conformity to postconventional moral reasoning. Rather than treating values as "contents to be transmitted," this theory helps design educational situations that stimulate judgment and deliberation over value conflicts, demanding multiple justifications and perspectives (Mezirow, 2000). In postmodern logic, the emphasis is on reflective dialogue and the negotiation of meaning, not on the uncritical inoculation of dogmas. Integrating the framework of Kohlberg's perspective with RFCDC and ESD allows for the construction of a training path in which students move from simple value statements to reasoned reasoning and responsible actions.

At the same time, the international context marked by nationalism and extremism calls for a clarification, understanding and repositioning of the central values of democracy: human dignity, fundamental rights and freedoms, the rule of law, pluralism, active tolerance, nonviolence and rational deliberation in the

public space. Comparative reports on democratic decline and pressure on the press and civil society suggest that education must once again become the moral infrastructure of democracy - a place where coexistence in difference is not just a textbook topic, but common practice (Freedom House, 2024; International IDEA, 2025).

Starting from this, our study proposes a point of view according to which education through values, understood postmodernly, does not give up the aspiration of common landmarks, but re-signifies them through tools of critical thinking, deliberation and responsibility for consequences. It calls for teacher training oriented towards the foundation and connection of knowledge to values, the facilitation of moral dialogue and the design of authentic experiences (service-learning, community projects, simulated public deliberations), as well as youth training focused on civic engagement and democratic literacy. In the following sections, using integrated qualitative research methods such as participatory observation of social realities and content analysis, we will operationalize this thesis: (a) by clarifying theoretical concepts and models (including Lawrence Kohlberg's theory of psycho-moral development), (b) by critically discussing the risks of relativism and the pitfalls of "declarative values", (c) by proposing a curricular integration framework anchored in the RFCDC and ESD, with mechanisms for authentic assessment of moral reasoning and action (Council of Europe, 2018; UNESCO, 2020; Sterling, 2010; Jickling & Wals, 2008, 2012; Smarandache et al., 2014; Vlăduțescu, 2014).

2. On education, values and psycho-moral development

Values education has been conceptualized, throughout the 20th century, as a central formative dimension of the educational process. It involves not only the transmission of moral norms, but also the formation of the capacity for moral

judgment and deliberation (Negovan, 2008; Avramescu, n.d.). In a complex and volatile world, values education is responsible for the development of axiological competences – that is, the capacity to identify, analyze and prioritize values in a multicultural ethical context (Mezirow, 2000).

Sterling emphasizes that in contemporary education, values can no longer be taught as immutable dogmas, but must be experienced, reflected and critically assumed (Sterling, 2010). The teacher becomes a facilitator of meanings, capable of constructing educational situations in which values are discussed, not imposed. Thus, education through values means the development of an autonomous moral conscience, not conformity (Kohlberg, 1981).

At the same time, UNESCO (2020) highlights that the values of sustainability, such as social justice, equity, solidarity and respect for diversity, are essential for the sustainability of contemporary democracies. These become survival values in a century of crises – ecological, ethical, identity.

In the postmodern paradigm, education is reinterpreted as a space of epistemological plurality, negotiation of meanings and democratization of knowledge (Lyotard, 1979; Bauman, 1993; Giroux, 1997). The student and the teacher become actors of the dialogue, and the truth is perceived as situational and contextual. This perspective encourages tolerance and diversity, but also brings risks: the excessive relativization of moral benchmarks, the loss of ethical consensus and the emergence of a “value anemia” (Bauman, 1993).

At the same time, the postmodern environment is dominated by the identity dislocation produced by globalization, digitalization and migration, which reactivates reflexes of cultural self-defense. We thus note that in many contexts, this dynamic has favored the return to nationalist and exclusionary discourses, which propose a rigid collective identity in opposition to otherness (Freedom House, 2024, 2025). Contemporary nationalism, fueled by social

networks and media polarization, is based on rhetorics of purity, tradition and control, rejecting the central values of democracy – pluralism, inclusion and equal rights (Council of Europe, 2018).

Postmodern education therefore has a paradoxical mission: to value pluralism without losing moral coherence. As Giroux (1997) points out, democracy cannot survive without a “pedagogy of resistance” that confronts discourses of exclusion and hatred. In school, this resistance takes the form of education through democratic values, based on dialogue, empathy, critical thinking and active participation. The theory of moral development formulated by Lawrence Kohlberg (1981, 1984) provides an essential psychological framework for understanding how moral judgment is formed. The author describes moral development as a transition from an orientation towards immediate consequences to the assumption of social norms, so that, in its most advanced forms, moral judgment is based on general principles of justice. This evolution does not occur automatically, but is formed gradually, through experiences and educational contexts that provoke moral reflection.

Values education in a mature democracy aims to reach the post-conventional level, where the individual is able to criticize unjust laws, to argue ethically and to act according to moral principles, not social pressure. This is the stage in which the pupil or student becomes a reflective citizen, capable of empathy and moral deliberation (Kohlberg, 1984; Mezirow, 2000). Integrating Kohlberg’s theory into postmodern education involves creating open moral situations, not imposing a single moral code. Dilemma discussions, simulated public debates and collective reflection stimulate the transition from conformity to moral reasoning. In this sense, the democratic competences described by the Council of Europe (2018) – responsibility, respect for dignity, social justice, spirit

of cooperation – can be considered applied benchmarks of higher stages of moral development.

In a context rife with nationalist discourses, Kohlberg’s theory offers an anti-segregationist pedagogical tool. Moral education based on dialogue, reflection and value universalism counteracts the temptation of tribal morality (“us vs. others”). It cultivates moral autonomy, not cultural obedience – precisely what democracy needs to regenerate itself in a world of pluralism. As UNESCO (2020) shows, education for sustainable development and global citizenship must integrate the ethical dimension of solidarity and collective responsibility. Democratic values cannot simply be “presented”, but must be lived in collaborative learning contexts, where students confront the reality of difference. Thus, values education in the postmodern era becomes an act of democratic resistance: a reaffirmation of the principles of equality, freedom and human dignity in the face of the temptation of nationalist withdrawal. It is not about denying identities, but about articulating them within an ethical framework of coexistence. As Bauman (1993) noted, true ethics begins "when the other enters the horizon of our responsibility."

3. Education through values - descriptive and critical analysis

Postmodern society is marked by an axiological ambivalence: while promoting individual freedom and pluralism, it also produces a sense of moral disorientation, amid the relativization of traditional benchmarks (Bauman, 1993; Lyotard, 1979). This state of “moral liquidity”, as Bauman calls it, is reflected in education through the absence of common ethical benchmarks and the difficulty of speaking about good and evil without being suspected of moralism, of ethical exaggeration.

Education has become, in this contextual framework, a space for permanent negotiation between individual, cultural and ideological values. In schools and universities, the emphasis on performance and technical skills has eclipsed the axiological component (Sterling, 2010). The result is an informed but often morally unanchored generation, which manifests passive tolerance but not civic involvement. As Jickling and Wals (2012) note, discourses of education for sustainability can become superficial if they do not reach the critical and moral dimension of collective responsibility.

At the same time, we cannot help but notice that the digital environment accentuates the polarization and radicalization of public discourse, reducing the complexity of moral debates to immediate emotional reactions. Pupils and students live in an informational climate saturated with opinions, but poor in rational judgments (Giroux, 1997). In this reality, education through values can no longer be considered a simple field of “civic education”, but becomes a practice of cognitive and moral hygiene: learning to discern between truth and manipulation, between solidarity and hatred, between criticism and contempt.

In this context, the growing manifestation of nationalism and extremism represents one of the most serious challenges to democracy today. The Freedom in the World 2024 report shows a sharp decline in civil liberties in 52 countries, accompanied by the strengthening of discourses that justify the exclusion of minorities and the restriction of pluralism (Freedom House, 2024). In Europe and elsewhere, populist rhetoric transforms social discontent and frustration into hatred of the “other”, promoting segregation in the name of national identity. This phenomenon is amplified by authoritarian nostalgia: a desire for “moral order” and “restoration of traditional values”, falsely presented as a solution to postmodern uncertainty (International IDEA, 2025). In reality, such discourses

instrumentalize values – replacing moral autonomy with ideological obedience and civic solidarity with cultural uniformity.

In contrast, the values of democracy – freedom, equality, pluralism, participation and respect for dignity – have a universalistic moral structure, consistent with the higher stages of moral development in Kohlberg’s theory (1984). These values are not “culturally neutral”, but constitute the condition for the possibility of dialogue between cultures and identities.

Therefore, in an era of fragmentation, education becomes the moral guarantee of democracy. It is intended to form citizens capable of overcoming conventional morality – based on group loyalty – and reaching post-conventional morality, based on rational principles and universal compassion (Kohlberg, 1981; Council of Europe, 2018). School and university can no longer be just spaces for cognitive training, but must become laboratories of democratic deliberation. As Giroux (1997) emphasizes, democratic pedagogy does not consist in transmitting dogmas of equality, but in training critical thinking that can recognize and confront injustice.

In this sense, the RFCDC framework (Council of Europe, 2018) offers an explicit educational architecture for combating segregation and xenophobia, by developing empathy, dialogue and critical thinking skills. Teachers are trained to detect cognitive biases and cultural stereotypes and to manage value conflicts in the school space, not through repression, but through disclosure, highlighting and moral deliberation.

Here they make their presence felt and the role of teachers and young people in the reconfiguration of value education is manifested:

a) The teacher as moral mediator and architect of dialogue

In the postmodern context, the teacher is no longer a bearer of absolute truths, but a moral mediator who guides students in the process of discovering

and substantiating their own values (Mezirow, 2000; Negovan, 2008). This role implies a double competence: personal reflexivity and the ability to facilitate sensitive dialogues on controversial topics (discrimination, gender, migration, religion). Teacher training should include modules on applied ethics, moral psychology and pedagogies of deliberation, which allow the application of Kohlberg's theory at the didactic level. Teachers who can guide students from conformist to autonomous morality are those who stimulate critical thinking without imposing prefabricated moral solutions (Kohlberg, 1984; Sterling, 2010).

UNESCO (2020) also recommends integrating ESD into initial and in-service teacher training, emphasizing the values of sustainability, global cooperation and intergenerational justice. This model links education for democracy and education for sustainable development, emphasizing that there is no democracy without an ethic of solidarity.

b) Young people as moral agents and builders of pluralism
Complementarily, young people must be perceived not as “beneficiaries” of value education, but as active moral agents, capable of shaping democratic culture through action. According to OECD (2018), global competence involves empathy, recognition of interdependencies and the desire to act for the common good.

The mission of university and high school education is to promote formative experiences that allow for learning through action: civic engagement projects, simulated public deliberations, community campaigns and intercultural exchanges. These activities not only transmit values, but also train the ability to apply them ethically in real contexts. Thus, training young people for democracy means teaching them to think morally, not just to “be tolerant.” In a world where extremist voices promote separation, education for values becomes an education for encounter - between people, ideas, cultures.

4. The balance between pluralism and moral cohesion - a qualitative approach

From postmodern pluralism to shared moral responsibility

Postmodernism brought a significant gain in education: the recognition of epistemic and cultural diversity, of the right of each individual to construct their own meanings (Lyotard, 1979). However, this openness was accompanied by a collateral effect: the dissolution of common moral landmarks, often substituted by a radical relativism. In the name of freedom of thought, the moral neutralization of public discourse has been reached - everything becomes an "opinion", nothing is any longer a "rationally justifiable belief". Even worse: opinion, most often uninformed and self-interested, becomes a system of reference. In this context, education can no longer avoid the fundamental question: How do we cultivate common moral values without returning to premodern dogmatism and without falling into postmodern cynicism?

The answer we propose through this study is reflective values education, anchored in democracy as a moral system of mutual responsibility. It is not about imposing a "list" of values, but about forming a moral competence that allows for the critical analysis of one's own options in relation to the common good.

In the spirit of Lawrence Kohlberg's theory (1981, 1984), moral education must create contexts of reflection and deliberation that allow for the transition from conventional morality (the nationalist basis of group loyalty) to postconventional morality (reasoning based on justice, equity and universality). Thus, democracy is not just a political framework, but a moral level of consciousness – the collective expression of higher stages of human moral development.

The values of democracy as the central axis of postmodern education

Democracy, in a profound sense, is not reduced to electoral procedures or freedom of expression. It is based on an internal moral code, consisting of values such as human dignity, equality, freedom, pluralism, solidarity and social justice (Council of Europe, 2018). These values constitute the ethical infrastructure of an open society, and education is the main instrument through which they can be cultivated and transmitted to younger generations.

However, in today's societies, this foundation is eroded by three trends:

1. Cultural nationalism, which redefines education as a process of "identity defense" and replaces the values of dialogue with loyalty to the dominant group.

2. Media populism, which simplifies complex moral dilemmas into binary oppositions ("us" vs. "them") and cultivates an emotional, not rational morality.

3. Consumerist individualism, which transforms values into products of personal choice, emptying them of their universal content.

In the face of these trends, education through democratic values must offer a moral countercurrent: not through coercion, but through argumentation, empathy and the experience of coexistence. Teachers and young people must be taught to think in terms of shared responsibility, not exclusive identity. As Jickling and Wals (2008, 2012) show, an authentic education for sustainability cannot avoid confronting issues of power, inequity and injustice; likewise, an education for democracy cannot be neutral towards exclusion, racism or intolerance. In both cases, the central value is moral responsibility for the consequences of individual and collective actions.

In this context, the need to construct and assume the roles of the teacher and the young person as reflective moral agents is increasingly apparent.

The teacher – facilitator of democratic consciousness

In the classical paradigm, the teacher was the bearer of epistemic and moral authority. In the postmodern paradigm, he becomes the facilitator of democratic consciousness (Giroux, 1997). His role is no longer to provide definitive moral answers, but to create frameworks of reflection in which pupils and students can confront real dilemmas, discussing them in an argumentative manner. Thus, deliberative moral pedagogy becomes an essential tool. Starting from Kohlberg's theory, the teacher can organize activities based on moral dilemmas, public debates, role-playing or simulated deliberations (Mezirow, 2000). The goal is to stimulate postconventional thinking – that is, reasoning based on universal principles and not on fear, reward or social pressure.

Teachers also need continuous reflective training. UNESCO (2020) emphasizes that training for sustainable education must include ethical, intercultural and civic competences, and OECD (2018) insists on the ability of teachers to develop global competences in students – the ability to analyze transnational problems and cooperate across cultural differences. In the face of discourses that promote segregation, the teacher has the moral mission of being a guardian of otherness – one who ensures that the voice of the “other” is heard and respected in the educational space.

The young person – reflective citizen and co-author of values

Young people cannot be considered simple recipients of values, but co-authors of democratic moral culture. Postmodern education recognizes their active role in defining meanings (Sterling, 2010). In this sense, training young people for democracy means offering them authentic opportunities for participation, not just theoretical lectures.

Models such as service learning, peer mediation or interethnic community projects allow the internalization of democratic values through action, not through memorization. In Mezirow's (2000) logic, transformative learning occurs

only when the experience provokes cognitive and moral dissonance, followed by critical reflection.

Young people must be encouraged to ask themselves difficult questions:

- What does freedom mean in a world where truth is manipulated?
- How do we defend dignity when the “other” is demonized?
- How can diversity be experienced without fear, but also without indifference?

The answers are not given “from above”, but are discovered together – the process itself being formative. Thus, values education becomes a democratic exercise in itself, not just a preparation for democracy. Therefore, the imperative of reconfiguring the axiological framework of education and its orientation towards an integrative paradigm appears, from Mezirow's perspective, education through values in the current postmodern context must be integrative, that is, to reconcile four dimensions:

1. Cognitive dimension - critical understanding of values and the historical/cultural contexts that shape them.

2. Emotional dimension - development of empathy and moral sensitivity towards the suffering of others.

3. Behavioral dimension - concrete moral action, oriented towards the common good.

4. Reflective dimension - the ability to evaluate one's own moral decisions and to rationally justify them.

This model reflects the convergence between Kohlberg's theory (cognitive moral development), the model of democratic competences (Council of Europe, 2018) and the paradigm of transformative learning (Mezirow, 2000; Sterling, 2010). Its implementation requires a change in institutional paradigm: schools and universities must become moral ecosystems, not just academic ones.

The evaluation of educational performance should include criteria of civic participation, ethical reflection and critical thinking, not just cognitive results.

Considering all these aspects, we cannot help but distinguish the global implications of understanding and experiencing democracy as the moral horizon of education. In an international context in which ideological violence and informational fragmentation are gaining ground, education through values acquires a new function: that of supporting the moral infrastructure of democracy. Freedom House (2025) and International IDEA (2025) warn that the decline of democracy is often preceded by the decline of civic and moral education. Thus, educational policies must be rethought in the sense of global value coherence, without ignoring cultural particularities. UNESCO (2020) proposes the concept of shared values for a shared future - an idea that responds exactly to the postmodern challenge: how do we maintain diversity without losing moral cohesion.

5. Conclusions and openings

We strongly support the thesis that education through values is not a secondary component of the educational process, but the foundation on which any knowledge with formative meaning is based. Without a clear axiological framework, education risks becoming a simple accumulation of information, devoid of human and social finality. As Negovan (2008) states, the educational act achieves its purpose only when it leads to the formation of a moral and reflective personality, not just to cognitive performance. In the postmodern era, this perspective becomes even more necessary. Lyotard (1979) and Bauman (1993) have shown that pluralism can degenerate into moral indifference when values no longer provide a common framework of meaning. Therefore, school must once again become the space in which knowledge is based on values, and values are understood through critical knowledge. This complementarity between

truth and good is essential for maintaining the balance between pluralism and social cohesion. In the absence of values, knowledge can be used instrumentally – for manipulation, exclusion or domination – losing its liberating function (Giroux, 1997). In contrast, when democratic values (freedom, dignity, solidarity, justice, responsibility) become the curricular basis of knowledge, education forms citizens capable of critical thinking, empathy and moral action. But for these mechanisms to work, values must be enunciated and put at the basis of knowledge.

Therefore, value precedes competence. Pupils and students must not only know what to do, but why to do it and how to choose morally between alternatives. Therefore, education through values must be transversal and constitutive, not thematic and episodic. Values are not taught in a single discipline, but are integrated into the structure of knowledge – in the way of teaching sciences, literature, mathematics, history. Each curricular content should be anchored in the moral question: What human value does this content express? Thus, training is not only informative, but formative, and education regains its role of constructing the human in man.

At the same time, in the face of the rise of nationalist and extremist discourses, education through democratic values becomes an act of moral resistance and a form of defense of freedom. The Freedom in the World 2025 report shows that the decline in the quality of democracy is associated with the degradation of civic and moral-value education (Freedom House, 2025). In this sense, education must oppose segregation and exclusion by promoting inclusion, empathy and cooperation as norms of community life (Council of Europe, 2018; UNESCO, 2020).

Reconfiguring the educational system around democratic values does not imply moral uniformity, but the harmonization of freedom with responsibility.

Democracy cannot exist without diversity, but neither can diversity without common moral standards. Therefore, values education has the role of keeping the dialogue alive between pluralism and moral coherence, between identity and solidarity, between knowledge and meaning. Teacher training is the key to this transformation. They must be prepared to be mediators of meanings, capable of linking knowledge to ethics and creating contexts of critical reflection. As Sterling (2010) shows, only teachers who understand education as a process of transformation can facilitate the transition from simple learning to moral awareness.

At the same time, young people must be involved as actors of values, not just as receptors. Values education must offer them the opportunity to practice democracy – to deliberate, to cooperate, to challenge injustice. In Mezirow's (2000) terms, true transformative learning occurs when the individual critically reevaluates his or her own assumptions and constructs a new moral perspective on the world.

In conclusion, education through values is the necessary condition for achieving the formative desideratum of education. Knowledge, no matter how advanced, cannot form responsible people without a moral foundation. In the postmodern era, in which truth is relativized and democracy is contested, values become not only pedagogical resources, but acts of moral resistance.

The education of the future cannot be neutral: it must be moral, reflexive and democratic, placing values at the basis of any cognitive approach. Only in this way can education preserve its original purpose – that of forming free, responsible and solidary people.

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